

PRACTICE OF *PRANAYAMA* AS A SUPPORTIVE MEASURE IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA: A REVIEW ARTICLE

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Abstract:

Background: Asthma is a major non-communicable disease (NCD) with prevalence of 3% in India. It is one of the most common diseases which has been described elaborately as *Tamaka Shwasa* in *Ayurveda* literature. There needs to be a multidimensional approach involving non-pharmacological strategies that helps patient to cope better with asthma in disease management along with pharmacological treatment. Various techniques such as rapid/slow breathing techniques, deep breathing, diaphragm use, breath holding sessions, nasal breathing which are used to regulate the differentiation of the respiratory rate over time in *pranayama*, can help to maintain breathing more accurately & effectively to control asthma symptoms.

Aim & Objective: This review aims to give utility of *Pranayama* in management of Asthma

Material & Methods: Ayurveda Literature, text books, journals, research papers, online database regarding Asthma & *Pranayama* are reviewed for the study.

Result:

In Asthma patients, rapid & shallow breathing reduces breathing efficiency which causes high level of distress, fear & anxiety particularly during Asthma attacks. *Pranayama* such as *Anulomvilom*, *Bhramari*, *Kapalbhati*, *Bhastrika*, *Ujjayi* along with *Omkara* chanting improves respiratory muscle strength & blood flow to peripheral muscle, delays muscle fatigue, helps in cleansing the secretions of wind pipes & increases lung compliance thereby reducing the sense of breathlessness.

Conclusion:

Pranayama can significantly improve the maximum inspiratory & expiratory pressures with altering the respiratory muscle strength, it decreases inhaler/bronchodilator use, improves Asthma symptoms, causes recoveries in breathing parameters & thus improves quality of life.

Introduction:

Asthma is a common chronic disease of the respiratory tract involving chronic airway inflammation, bronchial hyperactivity & changeable airflow limitation. It is a disease of airways that is characterized by increased responsiveness of the tracheobronchial tree to a multiplicity of stimuli. It is manifested physiologically by a widespread narrowing of the air passages, which may be relieved spontaneously or as a result of therapy^[1]

It is an important condition affecting between 100-150 million people around the globe, worldwide deaths from this condition have reached over 80,000 annually^[2] It has previously been estimated that the prevalence of asthma in India is about 3%(30 million patients) with a prevalence of 2.4% in adults aged >15 years & between 4% & 20% in children^[3]

Prolonged use of pharmacological agents can cause increased morbidity and financial burden for patients, especially in developing countries like India.^[4] This can be overcome by non-pharmacological alternative modalities like *yoga* and *pranayama* techniques. Studies in the past have shown the beneficial effects of various *asanas* and breathing exercises on bronchial asthma.^[5,6]

Ayurveda has described five types of *Shwasa Roga* and *Tamaka Shwasa* is one amongst them. *Tamaka Shwasa* is a “*Swatantra*” *Vyadhi* i.e., independent disease entity and having its own etiology, patho-physiology and management. *Shwasa Roga* has been considered as a *Yapya Vyadhi* (palliative).^[7] It is well co-related with bronchial asthma which results due to derangement of *Pranavah Srotasa* (respiratory system) in which *Prana Vayu* is vitiated that is unable to perform its normal physiologic function due to obstruction through cough and moves in upward direction (*Pratilom Gati*).^[8]

The most common treatment is to use an inhaler, which delivers medication directly to the lungs. It help control the disease & enable people to live active life.

Two main types of Inhaler:

1. Bronchodilators (such as Salbutamol) opens the air passage
2. Steroids (such as Beclometasone) reduce inflammation in the air passage

Need for Non-Pharmacological management:

Initially inhaled/oral medicinal therapy is helpful in management of the disease, but later on there is increase in financial burden, morbidity (More and more patients requiring oxygen therapy/respiratory support therapy) and mortality. Bronchial asthma is a chronic disease, which has a high rate of death. Medical intervention is very expensive and has many severe side effects. With chronic inflammation of the airways there also present a psychosomatic imbalance and an increased vagal tone^[9, 10] These days, complementary medicine therapy which is a non-pharmacological enhances the probability of health consciousness with a positive outcome.

Pranayama: According to *Yoga sutra* of *Patanjali*, which is most authoritative book on *Yoga* in India, *Pranayama* is the fourth limb of the eight fold holistic process defined as *Yoga*^[11] “*Pranayama*” is a Sanskrit word, meaning development of control on breathing, it also said as the different forms of energy in the universe^[12] Breathing improves the efficiency of respiratory muscle and lung compliance during inspiration by reducing the elastic and viscous resistance of lung.

Aim & Objective:

This review aims to give utility of *Pranayama* in management of Bronchial Asthma

Material & Methods: *Ayurveda* Literature, text books, journals, research papers, online database regarding Asthma & *Pranayama* are reviewed for the study.

Asthma disease Review:

Asthma is a disease of airways that is characterized by increased responsiveness of the tracheobronchial tree to a variety of stimuli resulting in widespread spasmodic narrowing of the air passages which may be relieved spontaneously or by therapy. Asthma is an episodic disease manifested clinically by paroxysms of dyspnea, cough and wheezing. However, a severe and unremitting form of the disease termed status asthmaticus may prove fatal.^[13]

Prevalence^[14]: Asthma is very common; it is estimated that 5 to 10 percent of the population worldwide is affected. Bronchial asthma occurs at all ages but predominantly in early life. About one-half of cases develop before age 10, and another third occur before age 40. In childhood, there is 2:1 male/female preponderance, but the sex ratio equalizes by age 30.

Etiopathogenesis and Types^[15]

Based on the stimuli initiating bronchial asthma, two broad etiologic types are traditionally described: extrinsic (allergic, atopic) and intrinsic (idiosyncratic, non-atopic) asthma. A third type is a mixed pattern in which the features do not fit clearly into either of the two main types.

1. Extrinsic (Atopic, Allergic) Asthma

This is the most common type of asthma. It usually begins in childhood or in early adult life. Most patients of this type of asthma have personal and/or family history of preceding allergic diseases such as rhinitis, urticaria or infantile eczema. Hypersensitivity to various extrinsic antigenic substances or allergens is usually present in these cases. Most of these allergens cause ill effects by inhalation e.g. house dust, pollens, animal danders, moulds etc. occupational asthma stimulated by fumes, gases, organic and chemical dusts is a variant of extrinsic asthma.

There is increased level of IgE in the serum and positive skin test with the specific offending inhaled antigen representing an IgE-mediated type 1 hypersensitivity reaction which includes an 'acute immediate response' and a 'late phase reaction'.

- Acute immediate response is initiated by IgE - sensitised mast cells on the mucosal surface. Mast cells on degranulation release mediators like histamine, leukotrienes, prostaglandins, platelet activating factor and chemotactic factors for eosinophils and neutrophils. The net effects of these mediators are bronchoconstriction, oedema, mucus hypersecretion and accumulation of eosinophils and neutrophils.
- Late phase reaction follows the acute immediate response and is responsible for the prolonged manifestations of asthma. It is caused by excessive mobilization of blood leucocytes that include basophils besides eosinophils and neutrophils. These result in further release of mediators which accentuate the above-mentioned effects. In addition, inflammatory injury is caused by neutrophils and by major basic protein (MBP) of eosinophils.

2. Intrinsic (Idiosyncratic, Non-Atopic) Asthma

This type of Asthma develops later in adult life with negative personal or family history of allergy, negative skin test and normal serum levels of IgE. Most of these patients develop typical symptom-complex after an upper respiratory tract infection by viruses. Associated nasal polypi and chronic bronchitis are commonly present. There are no recognizable allergens but about 10% of patients become hypersensitivity to drugs, most notably to small doses of aspirin (aspirin-sensitive asthma).

3. Mixed Type: Many patients do not clearly fit into either of the above two categories and have mixed features of both. Those patients who develop the disease late tend to be non-allergic. Either type of asthma can be precipitated by cold, exercise and emotional stress.

Disease Review through *Ayurveda*:

The disease is called *Tamaka* as attack of the disease precipitate during night and during the state of attack Dyspnoea becomes so severe that patient feels entering into the darkness.

Types of *Tamaka Shwasa*: *Charaka* has mentioned two-allied condition of *Tamaka Shwasa* known as two types or further complication of disease proper i.e., *Pratamaka* and *Santamaka*. *Sushruta* and *Vagbhata* have only mentioned the name as *Pratamaka*, which includes clinical manifestation of *Santamaka*.^[16]

***Pratamaka Shwasa*:** When Patients suffering from *Tamaka Shwasa* gets afflicted with fever and fainting, the condition is called as *Pratamaka Shwasa*. It is suggestive of involvement of *Pittadosha* in *Pratamaka Shwasa*. It is aggravated by *Udavarta*, Dust, Indigestion, Humidity (*Kleda*), suppression of natural urges, *Tamoguna*, Darkness and gets alleviated instantaneously by cooling regimens.^[17]

As a matter of fact, cooling regimen is one of the causative factors of *Tamaka Shwasa* but in *Pratamaka Shwasa*, the patient gets relief by administering cooling agents due to *Pitta Dosha* involvement.

***Santamaka Shwasa*:** When the patients of *Pratamaka Shwasa* feels submerged in darkness, the condition is called as *Santamaka Shwasa*.

Though *Chakrapani* has mentioned these two as synonyms of each other *Charaka* refers them as two different ailments representing two different conditions of *Tamaka Shwasa*, these two conditions differ from each other according to intensity of attack.^[18]

Bronchial Asthma & *Pranayama*:

Pranayama represents a simple self-control technique and involves increasing an individual's breath awareness^[19]

Pranayama is useful to alleviate stress and reduce attacks of asthma and it might help in reducing number of hospitalization and expenses on drug. *Pranayama* showed a significant improvement in the vital parameters for the patients of bronchial asthma.

Patients with asthma use their auxiliary breathing muscles more as a result of a decrease in chronic inflammation and expiratory air flow in chronic asthma. This causes air hunger in patients who then resort to limited, rapid, and shallow breathing through their mouth. These changes reduce breathing efficiency and deep breathing ability. In addition, respiratory distress causes high levels of distress, fear, and anxiety, particularly during asthma attacks. These dysfunctional breathing patterns in asthma can worsen asthma symptoms [20,21,22]. Conscious breathing patterns are intended to replace

these weak breathing patterns using *pranayama*. Various techniques such as rapid/slow breathing techniques, deep breathing, diaphragm use, breath-holding sessions, nasal breathing, which are used to regulate the differentiation of the respiratory rate over time in *pranayama*, can help to maintain breathing more accurately and effectively and to thereby control asthma symptoms [19,20,21]

Breathing Exercises[4]

1. Deep breathing (deep inspiration and deep expiration): subjects sit in *Sukhasana* and perform deep inspiration and expiration through both nostrils.
2. *Sasankasana* breathing: subjects sit in *vajrasana* with their hands back, holding the right wrist with the left arm, with inhalation the person bends backward and with exhalation bends forward touching his/her forehead to the ground.
3. *Anuloma viloma*: common breathing practice, in which subjects breathe through alternate nostrils while sitting in *Sukhasana*.
4. *Bhramari* chanting: sitting in *Sukhasana* subjects inhale through both nostrils and while exhaling produce sound of female humming bee.
5. *Omkaara* (modified): commonly used for meditation, but not included in regular breathing exercises, is an important exhalation exercise. Changes to this exercise, keeping in mind the asthmatic expiratory difficulty with air trapping, were made so as to strengthen expiration. Patients were advised to sit in *Sukhasana* and to inhale deeply and then while exhaling produce Omkaara with maximum force and to continue until further exhalation is not possible.

During conventional *Omkaara*, *Omkaara* is pronounced as ooooo...mmm, but patients were advised to practice **OOOOOOOOO...MMM** (high pitch/forceful) with prolonged exhalation.

During normal *Omkaara* the air comes out only from the upper part of airways, but asthma is a disease that affects whole lower respiratory tract so prolonged exercise which helps to expire maximum trapped air is found beneficial . Normally, *Omkaara* is stopped after 10–15 seconds like

ooooo...mmm, but the beneficial effect in asthma is found with prolonged **OOOOOOOOOOOOOO...MMMM** until further expiration is not possible.

First three breathing practices are to normalize the breathing, while *Bhramari* and *Omkaara* are expiratory exercises.

Effect on Respiratory Rate:

Many studies have shown the improvement in respiratory rate. The fall in blood pressure in yoga-trained subject may be due to a decreased sympathetic force caused by **Pranayama** leading to decreased peripheral resistance in the blood vessels[23] While doing *Pranayama* the skeletal muscles were relaxed and thus a closed continued voluntary control created over respiratory muscles and it may reduce the rate of respiration to a great deal. It has been claimed that yoga practice brings about a significant reduction in basal oxygen demand.[24]

Effect on the Pulmonary Function Tests:

Number of studies shows the changes in the pulmonary function tests like FVC, FEV1, ratio of FEV1/FVC and PEFV.[25, 26] It is supposed that the mechanism of improvement in respiratory indicators may be due to the characteristics of *Pranayama yoga* in collaboration of breathing techniques, exhale and inhale. It is proved from different studies that breathing exercise helps in cleansing the secretions of air pipes and increases lung compliance. When the lung compliances increased, breathing becomes comfortable and respiratory muscle strength is improved. *Yoga asanas* and *Pranayama* improve the various lung volumes, lung capacities, and pressures in young adult.

Effect on Respiratory muscle strength in chronic asthmatics.

Bhastrika pranayama is very beneficial to increase the strength of respiratory muscle. In normal shallow breathing, lung spaces are not used, whereas *Pranayama* helps in using lung spaces with the

help of respiratory muscle. Therefore, the peak expiratory flow rate is increased which might be an important reason for opening small airway in the lungs. *Pranayama* creates negative and positive pressures in thoracic compartment to improve its capacity and also increases the expiratory and inspiratory muscle performance. [21] During Pranayamic breathing, the lungs and chest get inflated and deflated to the fullest possible; this extent leads the muscles to work maximally which causes strengthening of respiratory muscles. [22]

Result:

In Asthma patients, rapid & shallow breathing reduces breathing efficiency which causes high level of distress, fear & anxiety particularly during Asthma attacks. *Pranayama* such as *Anulomvilom*, *Bhramari*, *Kapalbhati*, *Bhastrika*, *Ujjayi* along with *Omkara* chanting improves respiratory muscle strength & blood flow to peripheral muscle, delays muscle fatigue, helps in cleansing the secretions of wind pipes & increases lung compliance thereby reducing the sense of breathlessness.

In Asthma, with chronic inflammation of the airways there also present a psychosomatic imbalance and an increased vagal tone. These days, complementary medicine therapy which is a non-pharmacological enhances the probability of health consciousness with a positive outcome.

Conscious breathing patterns are intended to replace these weak breathing patterns using *pranayama*. Various techniques such as rapid/slow breathing techniques, deep breathing, diaphragm use, breath-holding sessions, nasal breathing, which are used to regulate the differentiation of the respiratory rate over time in *pranayama*, can help to maintain breathing more accurately and effectively and to thereby control asthma symptoms

Discussion:

This review study has enlightened recent information about disease. Bronchial asthma is the common respiratory disease of the current scenario which has been increasing in incidence worldwide, is a morbid disease which can also be fatal & needs preventive & therapeutic approach.

It is a multifactor disease; clinically, it produces symptoms and signs like dyspnea (expiratory difficulty), cough, and wheezing. Pathologically, there is mucosal inflammation, collection of inflammatory mediators, bronchial constriction, air trapping, later on remodeling of airways. Presently, it is difficult to control all the triggers in a single patient. It is better to try to improve lung functions by exercises and to correct the pathology (common result to all the triggers)

Ayurveda through its harmless modalities like *yoga-pranayama* may be considered as the best approach.

In bronchial asthma expiration is difficult, so exercises that support expiration are beneficial. Forceful expiratory exercises (expiration) are helpful.

In a normal person, air is easily coming in and going out, but in an asthmatic patient air is coming in easily but during expiration there is closing of airways, and force is required to open the airways; hence. Prolonged expiratory exercises (expiration) are helpful.

Through the literature review, we get a clear idea of the disease & an attempt has been made to understand how *Pranayama* can help as a supportive measure in bronchial asthma.

References:

1. Harrison's principle of internal medicine with 14th edition
2. World Health Organization: Bronchial Asthma Fact sheet. Revised Jan 2000; No 206.
3. Aggarwal A N, Chaudhry K, Chhabra S K, et al. Prevalence and risk factors for bronchial asthma in Indian adults: a multicentre study. Indian J Chest Dis Allied Sci. 2006;48:13–22. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

4. Saxena T, Saxena M. The effect of various breathing exercises (pranayama) in patients with bronchial asthma of mild to moderate severity. *Int J Yoga* 2009;2:22-5.
5. Agnihotri S, Kant S, Mishra S, Singh R. Efficacy of yoga in mild to moderate persistent chronic bronchial asthma. *Indian J Tradit Knowl* 2016;15:337-40.
6. Sankar J, Das RR. Asthma-a disease of how we breathe: Role of breathing exercises and pranayam. *Indian J Pediatr* 2018;85:905-10.
7. Pt. Kashinath Shastri & Dr. Gourakha Nath Chaturvedi, *Charak Samhita, Vidhyotini Hindi Commentry, Vol-2, Hikkashwasa Chikitsa Adhyaya 17, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi Reprint 2017.*
8. Kaviraj Dr. Ambikadatta Shastri, Bhaisajyaratnavali, *Vidhyotini Hindi Commentry, Vol-1, Kasa Chikitsa Prakaran 15/127-129 & Hikka-Shwasa Chikitsa Prakaran 16/44-45, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi 16th edition 2002.*
9. Rimington LD, Davies DH, Low D, Pearson MG. Relationship between anxiety, depression, and morbidity in adult asthmatic patients. *Thorax* 2001; 56:266-71.
10. Thomas M, McKinley RK, Freeman E, Foy C. Prevalence of dysfunctional breathing in patients treated for asthma in primary care: A cross sectional survey. *BMJ* 2001;322:1098-100.
11. Hartranft C. *The Yoga-Sutra of Patanjali: A New Translation With Commentary.* India: Shambhala Classics; 2003. [Google Scholar]
12. Saraswati SS. *Asana Pranayama Mudra Bandha.* Patna: Bihar School of Yoga; 2006. p. 394-7
13. Mohan Harsh, *Textbook of pathology, 7th edition 2015, Ch. 15, Page no.464.*
14. Kasper Dennis L., Fauci Anthony S. et. Al., *Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine, 19th edition 2015, Mc Graw Hill Publication, Section 2/252, Page no. 1420-1421.*
15. Tripathi KD, *Essentials of Medical Pharmacology, 7th edition 2013, Chp. 16, Page no. 222, 232 & 233.*
16. Madhavakar, *Madhava Nidana, revised by Vijayarakshita and Kanthadatta 'Madhukosha' commentary with english translation by Prof. Himasagara Chandra*

Murthy, Published by Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, Varanasi, Edition 1, Year of publication 2006, Purvardha 12/15,pg no.175

17.Acharya J.T., Charaka Samhita, Chikitsasthana 17/19-20, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Banaras.

18.Sharma PV, Sushruta Samhita, Uttartantra 51/6, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Banaras.

19.C.A. Slader et al. Complementary and alternative medicine use in asthma: who is using what?

Respirology(2006)

20. D. Morse Yoga for asthma Int. J. Yoga Ther. (2007)

21. P. Sengupta Health impacts of yoga and pranayama: a state-of-the-art review Int. J. Prev. Med.(2012)

22. Manaf Yoga, Pranayama, Breath and Energy Control (2006)

23. Nagarathna R, Nagendra HR. Yoga for bronchial asthma: a controlled study. Br Med J 1985;291(6502):1077-9.

24. Goyeche JR, Ago Y, Ikemi Y. Asthma: the yoga perspective part I the somatopsychic imbalance in asthma: towards a holistic therapy. J Asthma Res 1980;17(3):111-21

25. Singh V, Wisniew SK, Britton T, et al. Effect of yoga breathing exercises (Pranayam) on airway reactivity in subjects with asthma. Lancet 1990;335(8702):1381-1383.

26. 20. Sodhi C, Singh S, Dandona PK. A study of the effect of yoga training on pulmonary functional in patients with bronchial asthma. Indian Journal Physiology Pharmacology 2008;53(2):169-174.